

DEVELOPMENT OF AUTOMATED DRY FIBRE PLACEMENT FOR HIGH RATE DEPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

The details for a lab scale automated dry fibre placement rig is given in this paper with the information on the real-time data transfer and high rate control (0.1ms) of the temperature and positional adjustments. This was designed to operate at speeds up to 3m/s deposition to determine the effects of machine parameters that surpass the limits of existing commercial machines. This was achieved by using EtherCAT technology to provide high sample rates and communications speeds between control and storage devices used for this rig. It assesses the current limitations to the deposition rate with the objective of reducing cycle time. Additionally, experimentation has been performed to demonstrate high heating rates ($>1000^{\circ}\text{C/s}$) and temperature control via a Joule heating approach, suitable for heating dry carbon fibre tows at response rates $<1\text{ms}$.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

As aircraft production rates increase towards 60 per month [1], the demand increases for highly automated manufacturing processes, such as Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) and Automated Tape Layup (ATL). These aim to produce repeatable complex laminate structures with aerospace precision. These processes are prolific for the production of wing skins and fuselages [2]. There is also recent interest within the automotive industry to utilize the low material wastage and general automatability by producing net-shaped preforms. These often require a secondary processing stage, such as forming or overmoulding, to enable higher levels of part complexity [3, 4]. However, these processes are still limited by the high material and processing costs to produce thermoset and thermoplastic prepreg slit-tapes. This has led to the demand for a dry fibre alternative. One option is the process referred to as automated dry fibre placement (ADFP), using binder coated tows or tapes which are deposited in strips before infusion. As a result of the low cohesion of these materials to the substrate, in comparison to tacky prepreg slit-tapes, increased fibre fuzzing and material variability, preforms are more susceptible to misalignment and ply gaps/overlaps. Traditionally, these therefore require greater in-process intervention or reduced deposition speeds to meet aerospace quality standards.

There is no standardised approach to machine architecture of AFP or ADFP, such as gantry or 6-axis robot with head mounted creels or creel cabinets. However, offline programming takes into account the machine kinematics (which may vary widely) to improve accuracy. The development of a component by fibre placement, typically follow that shown in Fig. 1, whereby the part is designed to the required specification, a tool-path is then generated from this to produce the preform before an infusion or consolidation stage and then inspecting the part (often by NDT methods). This is very costly, with considerable time and investment between the part design stage and the part inspection to determine how closely the final part resembles the initial design. This therefore depends on very accurate models of machine and material behaviour. In addition to that, consideration must be made for the transfer of a part geometry into the machine tool path to establish the best approach to achieving the desired fibre orientations, not characteristic of fabric forming processes, for example, whether the tool path follows a geodesic or parallel strategies [5].

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the existing ADFP part production.

ADFP process simulations are often complex with an extensive number of factors compounding into an overall part variability with no singular root-cause. Some of these factors include properties, which may be characterised analytically or experimentally, such as the materials thermal response [6], stiffness parameters [7, 8], tack performance [9, 10] or the compaction of pressure distribution of a particular machine/roller configuration [11]. However, a greater number of dynamic factors are overlooked because of their complexity and applicability to specific machine configurations or part geometry, and are therefore considered unfeasible to predict for every possible scenario. Examples of these include machine compliance, component wear, material variability caused by bobbin unwinding or manufacturing method, variability of previously deposited layers, latency or low cycle rates within the control and inaccuracies in predefined tool paths. This paper proposes that closed-loop control may be applied to alter motion and temperature parameters based on sensor data. It details a method of numerical control (NC) interpolation that enables decisions and alterations to be made via a PLC by locating them within the same industrial PC (IPC). This is opposed to the conventional G-code approaches, which require motion, feed and other output commands to be predefined, preventing feedback driven control from being utilised except to interrupt the process in the event of an error.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

This paper proposes a machine architecture independent, virtual process sequence for ADFP, which improves the control over deposition and has the potential to improve production rate by combining both real-time (RT) control (0.1ms) and online digital twin for simulation and inspection. This is shown in Fig. 2, where the coloured process blocks of the flow chart indicate the current areas of interest, whilst the highlighted region is the focus of this paper.

A high precision, high rate ADFP rig was also developed to demonstrate this at deposition rates up to 3m/s with a range of sensor data outputs for course-by-course control, and feedback driven online toolpath generation in the PLC in addition to the digital twin. This data enables further support with permeability simulation, quality inspection and machine learning.

This paper details the motivation behind these developments and the current limitations are overcome by introducing closed-loop not existing in typical AFP/ADFP machines. In addition, there will be focus on the data acquisition, which both the research and industry applications will benefit from the generation of a digital twin and sensor feedback. This will enable both positional control using surface measurements as well as temperature control via measured temperature data rather than constant temperature or power control methods [6].

Figure 2: Proposed flow diagram of the ADFP part production, from design to certification.

2 ADFP RIG DEVELOPMENT

A 4-axis deposition rig (Fig. 3) has been developed for high-speed deposition at a lab-scale. The deposition rate of this machine aims to achieve 3m/s for 1000mm centrally within the 2500mm x 600mm tool area. This therefore requires an acceleration of 9m/s². It is designed to deposit up to four 6.35mm

(1/4") tows, but can also deposit two 12.7mm (1/2") or one 25.4mm (1") dry tow with some minor adjustments to the belt configuration.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 3: Developed ADFP rig for high-speed deposition

2.1 Dynamics – High Rate Deposition

Although benefits of high deposition rates are evident, existing AFP and ADFP processes are often restricted up to 1000mm/s [6, 12]. This is because of the dynamic limitations, such as machine rigidity or the inertial response of large deposition heads, or physical limitations, such as the material adhesion or response rate of the control system. The ADFP rig is developed to overcome these issues by minimising the mass of the deposition head. Positioning the creel within a separate module reduces the head weight by >30kg for a 4 tow system, however fibres must be fed through a conductive channel to prevent variable distances between the creel and the head, and the friction that is caused by the electrostatic forces within the channel. The channels also constrain the tows to prevent fibre damage leading to fibre fuzzing by passing the tows through guides and eyelets. The fibre tension is controlled independently by servo motors, resulting in a greater accuracy and responsiveness for the control.

A Joule heating system has been incorporated into the head, which increases the fibre length, but enables both heating between the electrodes and heating between the electrode and the tool surface to minimise the temperature losses before the nip point. Prior to electrodes fibres are cut using a module that matches the deposition speed by engaging a shaft driven by the fibre feed and deposition rollers to the cutter module. This will enable investigation into the effects of cutting speed on the tows quality, whereby the cutting speed is usually reduced (less than 0.5m/s) in existing systems. After the cutter

modules, a large reinforced silicon belt constrains tows through to the nip point. This is to prevent tow wander, a phenomenon experienced when the tows are cut and tension is lost causing them to migrate laterally to the deposition direction.

The four belts and tows are then delivered to the nip point, a segmented roller enables $\pm 2\text{mm}$ independent travel in the Z-direction to improve pressure distribution over non-uniform geometry. This enables a low compliance material to be used, which will constrain the lateral position of the belts. The compaction force of the segmented roller is controlled by the servo motor which may either be torque or positionally controlled (to apply a force up to 1kN). Trailing this roller, a pneumatic actuator applies a force (up to 700N) to a second deposition roller, which continues to apply a force to the deposited material for a greater duration once making contact with the tool surface. This roller is also retractable, to prevent shearing of the deposited material in the event of steering the deposition. The deposition belt connects between the two rollers, ensuring that pressure is maintained between them whilst the tows begin to cool and adhere to the substrate.

2.2 Sensors

The primary objectives of this rig are to further understand and characterise the manufacturing process and the variability between a part design and the actual outcome in the form of a digital twin. To achieve this, the rig features three IR thermometers, axis encoders, a laser line scanner, a positional micrometre and a force torque sensor.

The contactless temperature measurement of the fibre before and after passing through the electrodes enables heating to be controlled and adjusted on-the-fly during the deposition process. These sensors are mounted to a pneumatic actuator to adjust their position, which enables different tows to be investigated. The third thermometer measures the temperature of the substrate ahead of the nip point to add a further degree of heating control, dependent on the cooling of the previously deposited material.

The axis encoders determine the position of each of the 4 axes. Although, the servo's each contain built-in encoders to establish position of each motor, these additional encoders measure the actual position once compliance of the machine assembly or error due to backlash are factored into the motion of the deposition of the head. These will enable greater accuracy to the motion of the machine whilst the difference between servo encoders and additional encoders will provide data into the compliance and backlash within the machine design.

The laser line scanner trails the deposition roller assembly to measure surface profiles, at a resolution of $2\mu\text{m}$, each used in real time to control the motion, 'course-by-course', using PLC interpolation of Bezier curves rather than predefined G-code or discretized toolpaths that are used in existing offline programmed layup. In addition to using this data in real time, the topology, position and orientation of each tow are transferred to a ring buffer and exported to a servo at 1s intervals via Ethernet. This enables a generation of a digital twin without causing delay to the cyclic control, which is then transferred to simulations, and assesses the quality of the preform in parallel to part infusion.

The positional micrometre, similar to the laser line scanner, measures the width of the tows across a profile. However, positioned either side of the tow, enables higher sampling rates and measurements of each tow prior to the deposition of the machine. This is currently used for characterisation purposes, measuring the variability in the width of the tow, as well as the lateral position of the material. If significant, this will provide further insight as to whether independent control of the lateral tow position is required to compensate or whether changing other machine or material parameters may reduce this impact.

A force/torque sensor, typically used in the robotic industry, obtains the forces and moments that act on the deposition head. These provide force and torque information in all 3 orientations. This will be used to measure both the compaction force as well as the resistance to motion in any direction. It will also later be developed into a kinematic control for a 3D deposition rig, whereby this data will provide a basis for determining how the deposition head is impacted by changes in tool geometry. Combining this with a feed forward control, where the part geometry is known, it will enable how normal-to-surface motion may be achieved on-the-fly, without the requirement of predefining the toolpath.

2.3 Control and Communication

In order to process this data, an Industrial PC (IPC) uses EtherCAT technology establish communication between a human-machine interface (HMI), server, the PLC, inputs and outputs (I/O), and Numerical Control (NC). The IPC is a Windows based system contains the PLC, I/O and NC within the same location, enabling real-time data exchange between each of them. The HMI and server are operated within a PC, which is connected to the IPC via Ethernet. The software that links the devices, TwinCAT (Beckhoff Automation) contains a built-in feature Automation Device Specification (ADS) which ensures that each device may send, receive and write data in real-time once communication is established. This is the backbone of the developed rig, simultaneously performing cyclic loops at a base rate of 0.1ms and performing cyclic tasks offset from one another to prevent latency. Combined with the ADS, enables large quantities of data to be exchanged between devices without impacting the motion or other RT control.

Although the EtherCAT technology allows for 0.1ms sampling rates, hardware such as the sensors and servo drives limit the rate for which the system may operate (Table 1). These sampling times have an effect on the adjustments during the high speed deposition processes. For example, travelling at 3m/s, a 2ms sampling rate suggests that the minimum travel distance before a change will be made is 6mm. Therefore, selecting a control that can surpass the hardware connected to it, prevents a ‘bottle-neck’ as the data is processed and exchanged between devices.

Component	Sampling rate (ms)	Limit
PLC (Base Rate)	0.1	Processing power
Heating	0.5	Solid state relay (opening/closing)
Force/torque sensor	1	Data output
Encoders	1	Data output
Servo drives	2	Terminals
Positional Micrometre	2	Data output
Laser Line Scanner	10	Exposure time to image carbon
IR Thermometer	150	Data output

Table 1: Sampling rates and limits for various sensors and

Factor	Unit	Levels
Rate	m/s	0.5, 1, 3, 5
Acceleration	m/s ²	0.5, 1, 5, 10
Part Area	m ²	0.5, 18, 72, 288
Aspect Ratio (Length/Width)	-	1, 2, 4, 8
Tow width	mm (inches)	3.175 (1/8”), 6.35 (1/4”), 12.7 (1/2”), 25.4 (1”)
Tows per course	-	1, 4, 8, 16
Number of plies	-	4, 8, 12, 16

Table 2: Factors and levels used for full-factorial analysis

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Full-factorial analysis - Rate Model

Firstly, to evaluate the rate limitations, a model determines the relative contribution of the ADFP machine and part parameters (individually and interactions) to production rate by performing full factorial analysis (Table 2). The model negates the dynamic limitations of the machine architecture and assumes a zig-zig tool path of each rectangular part with a quasi-isotropic layup. As there is no standard unit for quantifying rate of ADFP machines, separate conclusions were drawn in terms of kg/hr or parts per annum (ppa). The rate model operates by determining duration for each course along with the length of each tow. Assuming a bobbin contains 6kg of carbon fibre, this enabled the number of bobbin changes

to be quantified to determine the ‘downtime’ (3 minutes per bobbin change) of each structure. At this stage, it is assumed that 100% of the tows are successfully deposited, and therefore the only downtime experienced during manufacture is resultant from bobbin changes.

3.2 Heating experimentation

As part of the development of the high rate ADFP rig, multiple heating methods were considered: infrared (IR) heating, laser heating, flashlamp technology and Joule heating. IR heating is a common solution for its low cost, however the response rate can be large (up to 1s) making them only suitable for constant temperature deposition [6]. Laser heating significantly improves this heating rate and enables the temperature to be controlled by altering the laser power or shape [6]. However, laser heating is expensive whilst also posing safety issues for a lab scale rig. Flashlamp technology is a relatively new technology development, used pulsed light to enable high levels of control of temperature at the nip point by changing duration, frequency and energy of the light [13]. Although, this improves the safety of the heating over the laser heating, it is still an expensive option for a lab scale setup. The selected option was Joule heating, using the electrical conductivity in the fibre direction to generate heat once an electric current is induced into the material. This has previously been achieved for thermoplastic materials and has shown to improve bulk factor when producing thick preforms, by reducing heat transfer into the previously deposited materials compared to heating a nip-point, and is capable of high heating rates ($>4000^{\circ}\text{C/s}$) [14, 15].

To achieve deposition rates of 3m/s, heating rates of over 4500°C/s are required to heat the material within 95mm heating length. Therefore, to test the feasibility of this heating methodology, a table top test rig was set up (Fig. 4) to establish communication with the IPC, and measure the heating rates with respects to voltage. This used three copper electrodes positioned 47.5mm apart to enable both 47.5mm and 95mm heating lengths to be measured. The electrodes were compacted together via springs, and were insulated from the bearings and other apparatus by ceramic bushes. Two IR thermometers measured the temperature of the carbon tapes, half way between each of the electrodes.

Figure 4: Resistance heating testing rig for measuring the temperature response of carbon fibre at a rate of 150ms using IR thermometers

In addition to hardware, a UI was created on a connected PC, which transmitted data to and from the PLC in RT, with timestamps to ensure the measured data could be synchronized with motion data obtained from servo motor encoders. When transferring the data to the PC cyclically, every 2s, the PLC stored temperature data at to the ring buffer at a sampling rate governed by the limit of the three IR thermometers (150ms) before being transferred and deleted from the buffer every cycle. This method ensured that the PLC remained unaffected as the data was transferred between IPC and PC. Simultaneously, a separate ring buffer stored motion data from the servo drives at a rate of 2ms to demonstrate that the large quantities of data could be transferred by this method. The UI created is shown in Fig. 5, and shows how the IPC communication is established, live data is added to the text boxes, input data is sent to the IPC and graphs show temperature and motion data, updated every 2s once the tests have started. The data is then saved as a CSV file on the PC to be post processed.

Figure 5: UI for establishing RT two-way communication and data logging between data acquired in the PLC environment and the server (PC)

Figure 6: Graphical visualization of the I/O signal to for controlling temperature via TwinCAT Scopeview

Within the PLC, safety limitations were added to ensure that the current was cut upon exceeding 250°C. The current was applied cyclically to a single ¼” tape (Cytec DRY UD-24K IMS65-194-6.35), heated for 30s and cooled for 30s, three times at a range of voltages, incrementing 0.5V each time until a steady state temperature greater than the limit temperature was achieved. Proceeding this a second order exponent curve was fitted to the temperature/time curves for each period of heating and cooling. This data was then extrapolated to a higher voltage (30V), whereby a PID control was added to the PLC to demonstrate the temperature control ability. For this, a duty cycle time and frequency was used to control the heating (Fig. 6). This uses a digital I/O signal to control a solid-state relay (SSR) at duty cycle times as short as 1ms (minimum $t_{on}/t_{off} = 0.5ms$).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Full-factorial analysis - Rate Model

The percentage contributions of the rate model are shown in Fig. 7. This shows that the overall rate of the machine is largely governed by the part size and the course width. The primary contributions are part area of the preform (48.2%) when characterised by ppa and number of tows per course (31.3%) and tow width (21.3%), by kg/hr. However, in this simple model, it does not factor the complexity of the geometry, assuming it to rectangular, and therefore the reductions in rate as a result of non-uniform pressure distribution and increased head inertia are neglected. The results highlight the difference of the units used to measure the production rate. Parts per Annum (ppa) is a mainly influenced by part geometry whilst the unit itself has no indication of the overall quantity of material deposited. This unit is considered to be geometry specific and not suitable as a machine specification. It is therefore suggested that kg/hr is better suited to quantify the rate of a fibre placement machine, as this value may be

considered an upper limit, and therefore the impact of downtime can be quantified directly from this rate. For example, if a machine is capable of 30kg/hr but the machine is stopped to correct a failed tow for 10 minutes and 4 bobbins were changed (3 minutes) during a single hour, a simple calculation would determine the actual deposition rate to be 19 kg/hr.

Figure 7: Percentage effects of machine and part parameters.

Although the deposition rate of the machine showed some influence up to 3m/s, the increased distance required to achieve higher deposition rates therefore depends on greater acceleration or larger part area to benefit, indicated by the divergence of the results shown in Fig. 8a and 8b, respectively. The mean rates for changing tow width and number of tows show near linear trends. However, the number of bobbin changes each require generates the discrepancy between these variables. This is evident in Fig. 8c, which shows that although multiple combinations of tow width and number achieve equal course widths, higher rates are achieved by using wider tows as a result of the reduced number of bobbins and therefore bobbin changes they experience even though the quantity of material per bobbin remains equal, 6kg. For example, four 25.4mm (1”) tows can achieve a greater mean deposition rate, 35.0kg/hr, than sixteen 3.175mm (1/4”) tows, 22.6kg/hr.

Figure 8: Mean rates across full-factorial analysis study. Results combinations of (a) rate and acceleration, (b) rate and part area and (c) tow width and number of tows per course. The blue line indicates the average across all results, 27kg/hr.

4.2 Joule Heating Control

The initial trials were performed to determine the effects of tow length and compaction force applied to the electrodes to induce Joule heating into carbon fibre. Example results are shown in Fig. 9a, showing the temperature curves for varying voltage, heating times of 30s was sufficient to achieve steady state temperature for which 2nd order exponential curves could be fitted to determine the coefficients of Equation 1 and 2, each with R² values greater than 0.99.

$$T = ae^{bt} + ce^{dt} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = abe^{bt} + cde^{dt} \quad (2)$$

Figure 9: Joule heating results for carbon tow (L - 47.5mm, Compaction – 39N). (a) Raw data for varying voltage, (b) fitted temperature vs. time curves, (c) fitted heating rate vs. time curves and (d) heating rate vs. temperature.

Fig. 9b and 9c show the fitted curves and enable the heating rates to be determined with respects to temperature (Fig. 9d), which would be used for the temperature control. The 2nd order exponential curve fit may also be applied to the cooling rates, which was used for the temperature control. Fig. 10 demonstrates the effects of altering the length of the heating zone, L, and the compaction force of the electrodes. Reducing the distance between the electrodes reduces volume of heated material and the surface area of the convection and radiation heat losses. Additionally, reducing the heated length linearly reduces the resistance of the material and increases the current drawn for a constant voltage; from 1.8A (L – 95mm) to 2.4A (L – 47.5mm) at 5V. This therefore increases the degree of Joule heating. Initial results (Fig. 10) achieve greater than double the heating rate across the full temperature range at 5V when the compaction force remains constant and the length halved. Increasing the compaction force of the electrodes further increases the heating rate by reducing the contact resistance with the electrodes and therefore increases the degree of Joule heating by increasing the current further to 3.7A (at 5V).

Figure 10: Comparison between the fit curves for changing length of the heat

Temperature control was applied to the Joule heating test rig. This used greater voltages than what could be tested under steady state conditions due to the high temperatures and heating rates (up to 30V). This used a PID controller to determine the t_{on} time for a duty cycle, as shown in Fig. 6. An example of this is shown in Fig. 11, for a 8ms duty cycle and 30V supply, and demonstrates a changing set temperature despite a heating rate greater than what could be measured by the 150ms sampling rate ($>1000^{\circ}\text{C/s}$).

Figure 11: Demonstration of the temperature control for heating carbon fibre tows by Joule heating

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has detailed the development of the ADFP rig capable of using RT data acquisition and sensor feedback. Initially, this feedback has been used for temperature control during the heating of the fibre deposition, which has been demonstrated, but current work is investigating using additional data for positional adjustments and “course-by-course” changes to the toolpath determined by variability of the previously deposited tows. The design of this rig is capable of depositing at speeds of up to 3m/s, which requires high heating rates ($>4500^{\circ}\text{C/s}$) and fast response times ($<1\text{ms}$) which it has been determined that Joule heating is the most suitable method of heating.

The analysis of the rate model has shown that most informative method of charactering the rate of an ADFP process is by the volume of material deposited with respects to time, rather than production rate. This quantifies the machine performance in a non-part specific unit. It has also demonstrated deposition speed and acceleration are only part of the limitations to an ADFP machine, with interactions between multiple factors leading to influence in the deposition rate. However, it would also be of benefit to add a ‘robustness’ factor to this model, as this would enable machine downtime to be added to the analysis, which would be expected to have a significant impact on the results. Electroimpact propose a

suitable metric for quantifying robustness by “mean strips before failure” (MSBF) to provide ratio of the number of successful tows to failed tows during a manufacturing process [16].

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